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ABSTRACTS

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Single Cell Analysis to understand Cellular Heterogeneity and Transcriptome profile of Primary and Metastatic Tumors

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Abstract: Single-cell transcriptomic analysis is an effective way to study diseases like cancer which show multifaceted heterogeneity and constant evolution. Within this heterogeneous group, a certain genotype may be better adapted to spread and invade other body tissues. One of the hallmarks of cancer metastasis is the Epithelial-Mesenchymal (EMT) and Mesenchymal-Epithelial transition (MET). Between the two states (E and M) a third intermediate state is said to exist where cells express hybrid epithelial/mesenchymal markers (E/M) and show properties of drug resistance and tumor-initiating potential. Hence, timely identification and treatments that target these cells are important to terminate cancer progression to more advanced stages. In this study, the single cell transcriptomics profile of primary breast cancer and paired metastatic lymph node tumors in 8 breast cancer patients were analyzed using R packages like Seurat, SingleR for annotation, and Monocle3 for trajectory analysis. After pre-processing, the cells were clustered and annotated to distinguish the cancer cells from the other immune cells. The cancer cells were divided into three subgroups depending on the level of expression of Epithelial and Mesenchymal markers to identify those that are at the intermediate state (E/M hybrid). Furthermore, the differential expression analysis was done to compare the primary and secondary tumor site, in terms of cell-cell interaction and expression patterns. The trajectory analysis was performed to understand the evolution on the temporal scale in pseudo time that will explain the dynamic progression of cells to a metastatic state. Thus, it was found that the immune cells in the metastatic site are less active compared to the primary tumour and down regulate their antigen presentation pathway in primary breast cancer

Keywords: Single-cell transcriptomic analysis, heterogeneity, metastasis, hybrid epithelial/mesenchymal, primary breast cancer and paired metastatic lymph node, Seurat, trajectory analysis, cell-cell interaction.

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